

ENHANCING SPEAKING SKILLS IN EFL CLASSES: STRATEGIES AND METHODS

N.J.Saparbaeva

teacher

Secondary school №3, Taxiatah, Uzbekistan

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In the realm of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) education, fostering effective speaking skills is pivotal. The ability to communicate fluently and confidently in English is a key outcome of EFL instruction, yet it often poses a challenge for both students and educators. To bridge this gap, a variety of methods can be employed to generate and facilitate speaking skills. This thesis explores several effective strategies for enhancing speaking proficiency in EFL classrooms.

In this way, creating a supportive environment play a crucial role since a supportive learning environment is foundational for developing speaking skills. Students need to feel comfortable and encouraged to express themselves without fear of judgment and teachers can establish this environment by:

- Promoting a positive atmosphere;
- Encouraging peer support;

Incorporating interactive activities are crucial for engaging students and providing them with ample speaking practice. Below we will pay attention to some effective activities which can be effective while teaching.

- Role-Playing: Students take on different roles and act out scenarios relevant to their interests or real-life situations. This helps them practice language in context and develop spontaneity in speech. Role play activities is considered to be a good option to be implemented in teaching speaking and develop students' speaking skill [3]. Role play teaches vocabulary and everyday language to leaners. These are significant elements learners need to develop their communicative competence. It can be concluded that, role play improves learners' speaking skills [1].
- Debates and Discussions: Organizing debates or discussions on various topics encourages students to articulate their opinions and engage in critical thinking.
- Group Work: Collaborative projects and group discussions provide opportunities for students to practice speaking in a more natural, conversational setting.

The next step is utilizing technology. Technology can greatly enhance speaking practice and make learning more dynamic:

- Language Learning Apps: Tools like Duolingo, Babbel, or Rosetta Stone often include speaking exercises and pronunciation practice.
 - Online Speaking Platforms: Websites and apps such as Italki or HelloTalk connect students with native speakers for conversational practice.
 - Recording and Playback: Students can record their speeches or conversations and listen to them to self-evaluate and improve their pronunciation and fluency.
- Implementing task-based learning one of the crucial aspect because it focuses on using language as a tool to accomplish specific tasks. This approach can significantly improve speaking skills by:
- Setting real-life tasks: Design tasks that mimic real-life situations, such as making a phone call, giving a presentation, or conducting an interview.
 - Providing clear objectives: Ensure that tasks have clear, achievable goals to help students stay focused and motivated.

Task based language teaching (TBLT). Task-based learning is viewed as a solution for students who are struggling with their speaking, particularly in creating an optimal environment for EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students to improve their speaking skills. TBLT is a learner-centered approach; it has primary focus on the task completion, uses analytical approach and specifies learners' real-life communication needs. Furthermore, TBLT has an outline as a set of activities used by the learner for a communicative purpose in order to achieve an outcome [5]. Task based learning is an approach in teaching speaking, the teacher asks the students to perform tasks that resemble authentic, "real-life" situations [4].

Speaking skill is the most important skill to acquire foreign or second language learning. Among the four key language skills, speaking is deemed to be the most important skill in learning a foreign or second language. Brown and Yuke [2] say, "Speaking is the skill that the students will be judged upon most in real life situations". Regardless of its importance, teaching speaking skills have been undervalued and most of the EFL/ESL teachers have been continuing their teaching of speaking skills just as memorization of dialogues or repetition of drills. Nevertheless, the modern world demands for the requirement of communication skills for the learners and the English teachers have to teach the ELLs the needed skills so that they will improve their abilities in speaking and perform well in real-life situations. In the present EFL/ESL teaching environment, oral skills are completely neglected whereas employability depends more on communication than technology. As very less priority has been given to the important elements of language such as phonological,

morphological, semantic and syntactic aspects, it has become a major impediment for the ELLs to acquire the speaking skills among the learners of English. So far, more concentration has been given to reading and writing skills. After realizing the importance of oral communication skills, more emphasis is now laid on developing the speaking skills of the learners to pursue their studies successfully and excel in their fields once they finish their education. Moreover, English is the language of getting opportunities for employment and getting success to achieve the desired goals in life. Moreover, these speaking skills are also useful for professionals to develop their career. In addition to this, these speaking skills are more useful for the employees those who are working in business organizations to promote their businesses. It is also a known fact that excellent, outstanding and inspiring speakers highly motivate and win the hearts of the audience. As speaking skills play a vital role in many aspects, there is a need for EFL/ESL learners to concentrate more on them. Furthermore, the teachers are advised to implement several useful strategies in their classrooms in order to

involve the learners more on learning speaking skills in their English classrooms [6]

In conclusion, generating and facilitating speaking skills in EFL classes requires a multifaceted approach that blends supportive environments, interactive activities, technology, and consistent practice. By implementing these methods, educators can create a dynamic learning experience that enhances students' speaking proficiency and confidence. The ultimate goal is to empower students to communicate effectively and comfortably in English, preparing them for real-world interactions and lifelong learning.

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